

Nov 13, 2023

Storage & Revival of Oomycetes

DOI

<https://dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.n92ldmqw7l5b/v1>

Diana Lee¹

¹ICMP - Landcare Research

Diana Lee: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7861-3128>

Diana Lee

ICMP - Landcare Research

OPEN ACCESS

DOI: <https://dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.n92ldmqw7l5b/v1>

Protocol Citation: Diana Lee 2023. Storage & Revival of Oomycetes. **protocols.io**

<https://dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.n92ldmqw7l5b/v1>

License: This is an open access protocol distributed under the terms of the **[Creative Commons Attribution License](#)**, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited

Protocol status: Working

We use this protocol and it's working

Created: November 08, 2023

Last Modified: November 13, 2023

Protocol Integer ID: 90683

Keywords: Oomycetes, Oomycetes cryopreservation, Oomycetes Liquid Nitrogen, Phytophthora, Pythium, Cryopreservation, Phytophthora long term storage, Phytophthora cryopreservation, cryopreservation protocol for oomycete culture, revival of oomycetes cryopreservation, oomycetes cryopreservation, improved cryopreservation protocol, cryopreservation, oomycetes such as phytophthora, viability during liquid nitrogen storage, oomycete culture, liquid nitrogen storage, oomycete, programmable freezing equipment, using carbon filter paper, liquid nitrogen, phytophthora, carbon filter paper, term maintenance of these organism, organism

Abstract

Cryopreservation of oomycetes such as *Phytophthora* and *Pythium* species is essential for the long-term maintenance of these organisms. In this method we present an improved cryopreservation protocol for oomycete cultures, using carbon filter paper, to enhance their viability during liquid nitrogen storage with consistency. Our method benefits researchers working with these organisms by long-term, who do not have access to a programmable freezing equipment.

Guidelines

Here are some additional tips for storing and reviving chromists:

- Use young, actively growing cultures for storage.
- It is highly important to ensure hyphae does not get damaged during storage (steps 7-10)
- Ensure the cultured carbon filter strips are fully immersed in 10%-20% glycerol for 1-3 hours as some may display hydrophobicity.
- If the culture does not revive after the first attempt, try thawing another straw and using a different medium. Some species may prefer a solid medium such as Rye B agar, or a different broth such as V8. Addition of B-sitosterol (0.05g/L dissolved in small amount of dichloromethane) to rye broth may help with revival.
- If the culture still does not revive, store the culture in 20% glycerol.
- If liquid nitrogen is not available, this method should also work for long term storage of oomycetes at

 -80 °C

Materials

- Rye broth

Protocol

NAME

Rye Broth Recipe

CREATED BY

Diana Lee

Preview

- Carbon Filter Paper cut into strips

Equipment

Whatman® application specific filter, activated carbon loaded paper, Grade 72^{NAME}

Whatman

BRAND

WHA1872-050

SKU

<https://www.sigmaaldrich.com/NZ/en/product/aldrich/wha1872050>

LINK

- Mr Frosty

Equipment

Mr. Frosty Freezing Container

NAME

Thermo Scientific

BRAND

5100-0001

SKU

https://www.thermofisher.com/order/catalog/product/5100-0001?cid=ANZ_LPX_CO_0SE_GAW_NT_mr-frosty-freezing-container_7012t000000YF4J&gclid=EAlaIqobChMI7frz_MvBggMVDNMWBR3XYQdBEAAYASAAEgK3kPD_BwE

LI
N
K

- Glycerol solution (10%-20%)
- Petri dishes, non-vented
- Cryovials
- -80 °C Freezer
- Liquid Nitrogen Dewar

Troubleshooting

Safety warnings

- ❗ Follow safety protocols required for handling of liquid nitrogen.

Preparation of Oomycetes for Storage

- 1 Inoculate a small agar plug of the oomycete culture into a thin film of rye broth in a petri dish.
- 2 Incubate at 20 °C until mycelium has grown about 4-5cm in diameter.
- 3 Tear the mycelium mat and place the small pieces onto carbon filter paper strips laid out on rye agar (or V8, or PDA).
- 4 Incubate at 20 °C until dense aerial mycelium is observed growing on the strips, usually in 3-7 days. 1w
- 5 Tear off the cultured carbon filter strips from the agar and place 4-5 strips into a petri dish containing a thin film of rye broth.
- 6 Leave the strips in the broth for 16-24 hours, or longer if the culture is slow growing. This process allows the hyphae to repair any damage caused by being torn off the agar. 1d
- 7 Rinse the strips in two changes of 10-20% glycerol to remove as much rye broth as possible. You can do this by gently swirling the strips in glycerol solution inside a petri dish.
- 8 Place the strips in a petri dish of fresh 10% glycerol solution and leave it sitting for 1-3 hours (at least 3 hours if the culture is slow growing) for the glycerol to be up taken into the cells.
- 9 Dab as much liquid off from the strips onto sterile filter paper laid out onto an empty petri dish.
- 10 Place the strip into a cryovial using sterile equipment and fill the vial with 10% glycerol, ensuring the entire filter strip is immersed.
- 11 Freeze at -1 °C per minute., but not necessary.

Revival

2w

12 Immediately thaw the cryovial in water warmed to 30-40 °C

13 Place the culture strip into a petri dish containing rye broth.

14 Incubate at 20 °C for 7-14 days and watch for growth.

2w

15 Subculture the culture onto 10% V8 agar or PDA to check for contamination and morphology.